

Carlsberg Danmark A/S

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Life is lived forwards but understood backwards

Carlsberg Danmark is part of the Carlsberg Group, one of the world's three largest brewing conglomerates. The Carlsberg Group is represented in over 100 countries, has production facilities in 35 countries, owns 140 brands, and employs about 30,000 people. Every day, the Carlsberg Group sells the equivalent of approximately 114 million bottles of beer.

Carlsberg Danmark produces, supplies, and sells some of Denmark's most prominent brands in beer, water, and soft drinks, including Carlsberg, Tuborg, and Coca-Cola. The headquarters is in Valby, while most of the production takes place in Fredericia.

This case specifically concerns Carlsberg Danmark and should be viewed in this context.

Even though we are talking about a large, modern brewing company, the past and historical roots still play a significant role. The company was founded in 1847 and is heavily influenced by its strong culture: The founder, brewer J.C. Jacobsen (whose motto was: "Semper ardens" (Always burning)), the iconic physical environment in Valby, the significance of the Carlsberg Museum (Home of Carlsberg), the company's foundation-owned structure, corporate responsibility and support, a strong inclusive personnel policy ("We welcome everyone"), and a stable workforce. The significance of "heritage" frames the underlying platform and mindset, reinforced by factors such as the long tenure of employees (with many celebrating 40 and even 50 years of service). During the COVID-19 crisis, the culture was evident in the decision not to lay off staff, to decline government wage subsidies, and to convert a production line to make hand sanitiser. It is ingrained in the employees that the products unconditionally must reach the customers, even if it means working longer hours. Some new employees have found it hard to adapt, eventually leaving or being indirectly/gradually pushed out.

The inscription on the iconic Elephant Gate in Carlsberg Byen (HQ), Valby, reads:

"Laboremus pro patria" (Let us work for the fatherland).

"The brewery's mission must always be to develop production to the highest possible level of excellence, regardless of immediate gain, so that this brewery and its products can always be a model and an example to ensure that brewing in this country is maintained at a high and honorable level".

Or a more modern motto:

"Standard for the highest possible level of excellence".

This ethos permeates the company, which, in addition to its long history, is foundation-owned, driven by social goals, has obligations to society, provides significant financial support to it, and is so rooted in Danish soil that moving the business abroad is unthinkable. It instils a strong sense of pride and security for individual employees, contributing to employee retention and shaping their sense of right and wrong. "Carlsberg runs in the blood", as it has been said. It also means that the aim is not just to work for a better day today. It is to aim for a better tomorrow and a better society in the future.

A giant with a dominant position—but still vulnerable

Historically, Carlsberg Danmark, especially after its merger with Tuborg, has held an almost monopolistic position in Denmark for decades. Competitors historically played a minor role and posed little threat. However, increasing international competition, changing consumer habits, the rise of microbreweries, and more demanding customers (e.g., retail chains) have put increasing pressure on the company. The response has been to introduce the Jacobsen brand, make technological leaps, and invest heavily in production and supply chains. Yet the economy and profits have been under pressure at times.

Although this case study focuses on the COVID-19 crisis, Carlsberg Danmark is – due to its size and international profile – also subject to direct and significant impacts from the macro-environment. This currently includes conflicts between Ukraine and Russia, as well as in the Middle East. Supply chains are challenged, requiring the organisation to anticipate potential developments and respond accordingly. Even though external crises can make existing strategies and plans less useful, the company's unique ability to plan, structure, and implement action plans helps it navigate unpredictability and necessary course adjustments.

The competitive environment is intense, making it crucial to attract new customers and retain existing ones (e.g., bars and restaurants). Due to the pandemic, some business customers (including restaurants, bars, and supermarkets) shut down, forcing Carlsberg Danmark to help them restart after reopening, partly by involving consultants and engaging some of the truck drivers. This is expanded upon below.

The company is periodically influenced by the introduction of new management principles/systems. Currently, for example, 5S, where external consultants bring in lean tools, is not always seen as meaningful. It diverts time and attention from the critical task of brewing beer and sending it out to

customers. As one employee put it bluntly, "We run around in a hamster wheel and constantly have to deal with these gimmicks".

The industry attracts a certain type of person

The product brings taste, enjoyment, and social interaction into everyday life, with the highlights being summer festivals and major sporting events. Either the company's DNA attracts a specific type of person, or they are influenced by being employed here. The culture is direct and candid, with room for seriousness and salty humour, sometimes bordering on what modern standards of political correctness and caution would suggest.

Carlsberg Danmark's work environment seems to resemble those in the travel and hospitality industries, drawing a particular type of person. At first glance, it may seem like a traditional production company with the associated culture.

The cultural cocktail

The workforce (about 1,500 people) falls into three roughly equal groups: (1) commercial, (2) logistics (sales through restaurants, bars, cafes, and supermarkets), and (3) physical production (in the city of Fredericia). This creates different subcultures, but because the company has acquired other businesses, there are also product-specific subcultures (e.g., soda/cola vs. beer), as well as subcultures among individual production lines.

The company has a culture where "blue-collar" roles play a significant part, leading to an hourly wage-based culture, representing the traditional Danish/Nordic cooperation model.

Hands-on culture that fixes problems quickly and effectively

The COVID-19 pandemic, with its unprecedented organisational challenges, called for decisive action and quick decision-making. Carlsberg Danmark possesses this quality, as it is deeply ingrained in the organisation: "We have a problem; we fix it". This resilience often involves firefighting. Urgent issues must be resolved swiftly, but this can divert attention from longer-term efforts. The company is like a supertanker: Once it is moving, it gains momentum and travels quickly, but changing course can be difficult. The historical baggage (the traditional way of working and problem-solving) can be limiting. Even small changes and slight deviations can cause uncertainty and a sense that the past was better,

especially when the hardships of the past are forgotten. This makes it challenging to prepare for future challenges.

Problems are typically solved through networking (i.e., knowing someone who can help fix things) rather than through systems, rules, or formal processes/channels. New employees are advised, "You must quickly get to know people and build a network of those who can help you with your tasks and questions".

Carlsberg Danmark also has a pragmatic culture where things are called what they are, with production and hourly wage roles shaping the atmosphere. "It's healthy for a company to have hourly wage employees".

Regarding continuity and change: The extreme (short-term) operational focus is balanced by the long-term organisational culture and trusted relationships with various unions.

Safety, safety, safety...

"Safety is everything at Carlsberg..."

Brewing beer involves many risks. The brewing process can go wrong or be destroyed. Machinery, equipment, internal transportation, and the use of chemicals (e.g., ammonia) present safety risks, and the work processes can pose occupational health and safety challenges. Other risks occur in logistics and distribution (e.g., truck driving, handling heavy goods, difficult access points). Finally, there must be protection against criminal behaviour, such as theft of goods.

Safety is highly prioritised, including all types of Life Saving Rules (LSR): Machine operation, guarding, working at heights or in enclosed spaces, handling hazardous liquids, hygiene and cleanliness, safety instructions, vehicles and traffic, etc. Due to this high priority and considerable effort in the area, the incidence of work-related accidents is very low, but certain employee groups are exposed to the risk of wear and tear due to hard physical work, especially in distribution. (Over a typical workday, the total weight lifted can be around 8 tons, though it's lower than it used to be: over 20 tons.) Given this, it's noteworthy that the average age of collective agreement employees in Fredericia is about 50 years.

There are very few warnings or demands from the Danish Working Environment Authority, despite regular inspections. Workplace assessment (WPA) measurements are positive, and absenteeism is low, averaging just under 4 percent across employee groups. There's a "flurry of safety representatives", an overall safety organisation (HSC), and regular local meetings (board meetings) where safety is measured and discussed.

The local safety efforts are driven by the group's overarching strategy from the Swiss headquarters. If a safety issue is discovered in one location, it is immediately addressed with systems and requirements across the entire group. This can feel like overkill but reflects the company's ultimate prioritisation of safety.

Twice a year, a company visits to conduct brief health checks on all employees, especially night shift workers. Participation is optional.

There's a zero-tolerance policy for alcohol, harassment, discrimination, etc.

The dance between employer and trade unions

Carlsberg Danmark has evolved from being a classic, potentially hostile, and power-based example of traditional labour conflict into a company characterised by mutual respect and recognition of the necessity of the other party, reaching further with cooperation and shared goals in day-to-day operations. However, it's still largely an employer/employee-based workplace. The characteristic feature is that you can be in disagreement, but the conflict is set aside once the negotiation is over (in difficult cases, by escalating to higher-level organisations, like DI, to avoid direct confrontation). As someone said:

"We certainly have our battles. We can be extremely disagreeable, but once we leave the room, it's forgotten. We don't hold grudges".

Despite Carlsberg Danmark's overall synergy and cooperation between employer and employee, there's a notable difference between salaried and hourly wage employees. The level of unionisation is higher among hourly wage employees, with clearer agreements on wages and working conditions, and specific (potentially unpopular) management decisions are more likely to be cleared with union representatives among hourly wage employees than among salaried employees. Put bluntly: If a boss says to go slightly to the right from now on, there's a chance it will happen. If a boss says the same thing but gets union buy-in, employees/members can say whatever they want, but that's the way it's going to be!

There's a significant sense of being "in the same boat", contributing to something larger than yourself, and knowing that "what's good for Carlsberg Danmark is also good for me" because there is mutual dependency. The employer understands that "a happy cow gives more milk than an unhappy one", and the management task becomes easier when union representatives are involved in problem analysis, solution development, and communication to employees about the decisions made. It's economically beneficial to treat people well, and it's ingrained in the culture that you can't (or shouldn't) strike, as the product is essential and vital to society.

The sense of camaraderie is so strong that new employees, after just a few weeks, blend into the culture, become part of the wallpaper, and "say good morning when they come to work, because that's how the family culture is".

Carlsberg Danmark's crisis management has stood the test of time, largely due to the existing culture of cooperation and the flexibility and willingness to cooperate displayed by organisations, among others. Perhaps the image of the "hostile employer culture" is actually the temporary exception (the "Svanholm era", named after an ex-CEO), while the collaboration and loyalty extend back to the Jacobsen tradition.

The collaboration climate is typically "Danish design", with employees willing to speak their minds and management listening when they raise criticism or propose improvements. "When a Danish employee hears a "no", they see it as the path to understanding what it takes to get a "yes", rather than just doing what they're told, regardless of whether they agree or think it's a good idea". There are also examples of self-management, such as when the group of truck drivers internally set holiday plans (within certain boundaries established by management). The philosophy is that those affected by planning make the decisions, fostering flexibility and helpfulness when there's a need to accommodate colleagues. The alternative is centralised planning set by management without flexibility.

How did the company respond to the pandemic?

In the days leading up to the Prime Minister's lockdown announcement on March 11, 2020, top management called an emergency meeting to decide on immediate measures. These fell into four categories (in the following order of priority):

- Health and safety
- Supply to the market (i.e., keeping supply chains running because of the company's societal role)
- Employee engagement to prevent uncertainty and discouragement from spreading
- How to win in the market (with the notion that a crisis also brings opportunities).

Top management's perspective on the situation, how they planned to handle it, and the decision that work and production should continue and be maintained were communicated to all employees. The message was clear: "This is what we have decided, so you still need to come to work, but we are listening to concerns and uncertainty...".

The societal lockdown immediately impacted all parts of the organisation. Regarding customers, there was first a brief panic-buying wave, followed by the shutdown of the "on-trade" market (restaurants,

bars, etc.) because these venues were closed, leading to a sharp increase in the "off-trade" market (where products are purchased in one place, such as stores, and consumed elsewhere, typically at home). These abrupt changes required production, logistics, storage, and distribution adjustments (i.e., truck drivers and sales consultants in retail). As customers bought less frequently but in larger volumes, it changed the need for packaging sizes. Employees were transferred from "on-trade" to "off-trade," truck drivers and sales consultants worked more closely together in stores, communication with store staff changed, and driving routes were adjusted.

Internally, the initial reaction was nervousness and fear. The pandemic was known to be dangerous, potentially fatal, yet large employee groups at Carlsberg Danmark were forced to continue their usual work, potentially involving close contact with others, increasing the risk of infection. Given this, it was essential for the company to provide clear behavioural guidelines and give each employee the option to "pull the plug". If someone felt uncertain or exposed to unnecessary risk, they had both the responsibility and the opportunity to withdraw from the specific work situation.

Hygiene became a critical concern, requiring enormous effort, with the guiding principle that employee health and safety took precedence over everything else. The response was broad, covering protective equipment, physical contact guidelines, workspace layout, procedures, reporting, hotlines for questions, etc. The response had to be dynamic, with frequent updates from authorities, which Carlsberg Danmark followed without exception, believing that government guidance was always better than the company's own perception.

The many requirements and recommendations to minimise/avoid infection spread were complemented by giving each employee responsibility and the ability to decide how to work within these constraints. For example, if a sales consultant deemed a store too crowded during a visit, they could stop working and return at a better time.

The role of middle managers

The COVID-19 period placed significant demands on middle managers during and after the pandemic. They had to ensure the performance and output of their teams in a situation where all work conditions had been thrown into disarray. They were the extended arm of top management and ambassadors for changing course, following guidelines and requirements, regardless of their personal opinions. They were responsible for ensuring health and safety compliance, even as rules changed frequently and might seem inconvenient or unnecessary. They had to manage staff who were under stress and facing uncertainty, not only at work but also in their personal lives. Middle managers often had to communicate through Teams with employees, even when in-person contact was more appropriate. They had to engage with their teams more closely than before, balancing interest and care with

avoiding over-monitoring and control. Middle managers had to step into employees' lives, listen to their concerns, and sometimes make decisions regarding employees struggling with personal issues or the demands of remote work and the resulting isolation.

HR universe: What does it look like?

HR played a significant but somewhat strategic role during the pandemic, while operational HR tasks were handled locally in individual units, with the manager at the forefront. HR, based on its close contact with top management, helped formulate COVID-19 response guidelines, communicated them to the organisation, and aided in interpretation and understanding: "How should we act when...?". HR was also available when managers needed advice on specific problems arising in the field. HR had to find new ways to coach managers in the changed day-to-day reality.

HR's role also included maintaining employee engagement and addressing the psychological strains that COVID-19 could impose on staff. There was a strong awareness that COVID-19 generally, and remote work specifically, might be experienced differently by different employees/groups. Consequently, HR provided frameworks for flexible work arrangements.

All aspects of the HR universe were involved: competence development, job design, matching people to job functions, principles for work time and place (due to remote work), appraisal interviews, health and well-being measures, salaries, dismissals, etc.

The specific health and safety guidelines and requirements related to infection risk were handled by the health and safety organisation, not HR.

COVID-19 fostered organisational maturity

To summarise in one sentence: "We've become good at navigating chaos".

The pandemic was an extreme strain on all parts of the organisation: production, logistics, distribution, and administrative areas. For example, if a truck driver tested positive, contact tracing identified which colleagues they had been with, the vehicle was taken out of service for up to 72 hours, and calls were made to the customers on that driver's route.

In the administrative areas, people learned to work from home, lead virtually, show trust, and believe that employees were doing their jobs without constant supervision. Staff are judged by output, not by the number of work hours. Employees work until they raise their hands to seek advice and assistance.

The company, with its strong tradition of negotiation and collaboration with unions, quickly adjusted to the unprecedented situation, finding quick and effective solutions. This included smoothing out workloads, moving employees to different job functions where needed (e.g., truck drivers reassigned

to warehouse work, and warehouse staff handling office tasks in stores). Union representatives showed flexibility, and boundaries between job roles became more fluid. Earlier, there wasn't a need (or tradition) for flexibility. Now, it was just a matter of working across boundaries and covering for each other during illness or home isolation due to infection risks.

Some specific job/person-match initiatives were implemented to keep employees engaged during the pandemic, as large customer segments (e.g., bars and restaurants) were lost due to lockdowns:

- Reassigning employees to other job types (e.g., truck drivers taking on sales or customer-facing roles in the field)
- Taking on warehouse jobs
- Completing maintenance tasks that couldn't be addressed during regular busy periods
- Requiring or encouraging employees to use their accrued time off or holiday leave
- Providing training/competence development (e.g., drivers trained to operate other types of trucks)
- Offering attractive redundancy packages to older employees to allow them to retire.

There were two main reasons why employees accepted these job changes. The initiatives were agreed upon and aligned with union representatives, and there was a recognition that refusing to change could result in a total shutdown. Some employees were unhappy, particularly if they had intentionally built up a significant amount of overtime for a specific reason (e.g., early retirement), and were then forced to use it now.

The decision not to lay off staff during the pandemic was both notable and, in a way, controversial but logical: If you fire people now, you'll face staff shortages in the future, and rehiring will be challenging.

There was some grumbling during the pandemic, with scepticism about vaccines and concerns about the psychological effects of isolation and claustrophobia. It was a significant milestone when masks could be removed, allowing people to sit together during breaks and "see each other's smiles".

Communication

Communication played a significant role during the pandemic. Daily news updates were sent to employees. They came from various sources, including top management (the company's overall strategy and the appeal to "all being in the same boat"), the health and safety organisation (e.g., use of protective equipment, testing, rules for absence due to COVID-19), HR (guidelines and contact with

authorities), middle management (changes in work hours, measures to avoid physical contact and infection spread, adjustments to office spaces, break patterns, etc.), and direct supervisors. The connection between management and employees was crucial, especially for remote workers and those with decentralized roles (e.g., drivers). Physical meetings were held when possible (depending on restrictions), and videos were created with management and union representatives providing updates.

There was unavoidable fear within the organisation: Would (parts of) production need to shut down? Would there be furloughs? Would there be a total lockdown? Would certain market areas close (e.g., restaurants and bars)? HR initiated a system of regular check-ins by team leaders to ensure employees working from home were coping.

This evolution cannot be undone. The pandemic imposed significant demands on middle managers, particularly those overseeing remote employees and shift workers in production. It created a closer bond and more significant flexibility, as employees were reassigned to different roles due to business closures.

A specific example: Internal communication remains a priority at the distribution centre in Taastrup (in the Copenhagen area). Weekly information meetings are held for all drivers on Fridays, with presentations from management and union representatives. Additionally, morning meetings are held three times (at 5:00, 5:30, and 6:00 due to different start times). In the warehouse, there is a short status/transition meeting when switching shifts.

Resilience: Bounce-back or Phoenix?

The company has gained greater flexibility and a broader understanding of "people issues" as strategically important, particularly within the management team. You can't just run a business based on KPIs. The pandemic showed that you must focus on individuals rather than results. The day-to-day approach needs to change, involving employees and leaders earlier in the process, explaining the big "why" instead of simply announcing new rules with little explanation.

The collaboration across the value chain has increased significantly. The pandemic created such substantial pressure on all corners of the organisation that dialogue, cooperation, mutual aid, and resource reallocation across organisational boundaries became necessary, fostering a more holistic perspective.

The trust required for remote work among employees who could work from home (primarily salaried employees) is now a part of everyday life—it wasn't before.

The story of "on-trade" staff and logistics employees who ventured into retail because the restaurant/café market was shut down is a great example of how both the organisation and employees

handle crises when there's fundamental trust. This might also represent a new approach towards the "one-firm" ambition.

The pandemic has ushered in a new meeting culture where physical meetings are kept to a minimum, meetings are shorter, and travel is reduced. This has led to quicker decision-making. "In the past, we had to wait a month before the next cooperative committee meeting. Now, it's resolved informally, virtually, right away".

Managers and leaders are now more accessible even if they aren't physically present. There's a healthier meeting culture, improved collaboration, mutual respect, willingness to help others, and better feedback culture ("friendly advice"), while the old spirit and culture have returned.

The organisation is relatively flat and not very hierarchical, fostering an informal atmosphere and a belief that contact across organisational levels is welcome.

Individual employee awareness of the company, its challenges and opportunities, its various subcultures, and the necessary synergy between these is growing. Carlsberg Danmark has become more unified, fostering a more holistic view. Employees feel part of something larger – the company – and also part of a team.

A compelling example of the company's increased adaptability and readiness for change is the upcoming radical reorganisation of logistics and distribution in Sjælland (the region containing the capital of Copenhagen). Instead of picking items and loading trucks from the warehouse in Taastrup, trailers will be "pre-packed" in Fredericia for specific customer groups, then directly transferred to trucks in Taastrup for delivery. This has far-reaching consequences:

- Fewer employees are needed in the warehouse, and approximately 40 positions will be eliminated
- New trucks are required
- Drivers must be trained to operate these new trucks
- Routes will be adjusted/expanded due to the increased capacity of the new trucks.

This radically different approach disrupts previous practices and habits, causing uncertainty and some frustration. However, it has been relatively well-received due to the following factors:

- The broader frameworks and plans were developed in collaboration with employee representatives
- They were also communicated to employees by management and employee representatives together

- The implementation is gradual
- Cross-organisational working groups are established to ensure the necessary holistic thinking and optimisation
- Attractive redundancy packages are offered.

Carlsberg Danmark, even before the pandemic, was heavily influenced by planning, structures, and reporting. Although COVID-19 "came like a thief in the night", it has only strengthened the company's belief in the value of planning, as it provides predictability, transparency, vertical understanding (from top management to and from employees), coherence across the organisation, and smoother organisational processes.

What's on the horizon?

Carlsberg Danmark is impacted by global crises like Ukraine and the Middle East. The brewing industry is undergoing significant changes, including technological shifts. There's increasing societal awareness of the (harmful) effects of the company's products. Are they approaching the situation faced by the tobacco industry – becoming vilified and facing increasing regulations? What might EU regulations mean, such as new rules on working time registration (which would be a step backward compared to the current trust-based leadership and flexible working hours)?

On the other hand, the company has become more resilient and better at crisis management. The strict focus on a single strategy has been partly replaced by scenario planning, keeping multiple options in play and preparing for various possible futures. Hypotheses are established, scenarios are created based on these hypotheses, closely monitored, adjusted, and refined, and strategies are calibrated to the evolving future.

Carlsberg Danmark has also become greener and more sustainable. Water usage for brewing has been reduced from 7-8 litres to 2 litres per litre of beer. Energy use has dropped significantly, with the ability to switch between different energy sources.

From an employment policy perspective, Carlsberg Danmark doesn't suffer from the (inter)national trend of declining unionisation and weakened union power. Most collective agreement-based employees are organised, and there isn't a power- or conflict-based relationship between employer and employee organisations. The "weapons" used are communication, dialogue, education, problem-solving in a collaborative manner, and avoiding confrontation and "old-fashioned" negotiations that escalate to higher levels when conflicts arise.

The HR strategic wish list

Some of the tasks on the horizon include:

- Unifying Carlsberg Danmark across commercial and supply chain areas
- Creating and nurturing a broader understanding of the big "why" throughout the organisation
- Encouraging managers to be closer to employees (e.g., focusing on well-being)
- Managing generational differences (bridging the mindset of current (especially older) employees with the expectations of newer generations, which are sometimes unrealistic)
- Promoting diversity and inclusion
- Ensuring more freedom within established boundaries to encourage acceptance of differences and allow employees to shape their roles
- Making the company and culture less masculine
- Creating a modern workplace
- Addressing issues with older, worn-out employees.

Final thoughts

Carlsberg Danmark demonstrates how a culture can develop, mature, and over a couple of centuries become so ingrained that it serves as a foundation for all aspects of the organisation.

The company encompasses a paradoxical blend of "loose and tight". Culturally, everyone is aligned, and the mindset is programmed and collectively shared. Additionally, certain areas (e.g., safety) leave no room for deviation. Systems, requirements, procedures, and sanctions are always present. On the other hand, there's also (somewhat contradicting this) flexibility, room for initiative, and freedom for employees. Both management and staff are inclined toward a pragmatic approach to problem-solving. Requirements can be relaxed, allowing for flexibility, with the understanding that discussions can be intense but should end on a positive note. Flexibility and "room for everyone" require boundaries that aren't too rigid to avoid unnecessary conflict. As a manager, it's essential to know that flexibility can sometimes lead to issues, with varying consequences. It can range from, "Don't do that again", to a red card.

While the overarching company mantra previously revolved around "sales, sales, sales", words like safety, security, solidarity, responsibility, and holistic thinking have taken their place.

It takes significant leadership skills to master the balance between setting the stage (presenting pre-determined strategies, plans, and frameworks that are not up for negotiation) and, at the same time, involving employees and their representatives in implementation to get the best results locally (i.e., within our unit). Managers must explain "the big why" and build a cohesive team capable of navigating future changes. They must be able to harness and strengthen a trust-based collaboration with employees and their representatives.

Given this context, it can be cumbersome and frustrating when new management tools seem overly abstract, disconnected from reality, or disrespectful of the local context. Examples include 5S and Disc management profiles.

Note:

This case report is an outcome of the following research project:

Investigating the distinctive features and resilience of human resource management in the Nordic countries: A longitudinal and cross-national study

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Sponsor: Sveriges Riksbank

Grant administrator: Göteborgs Universitet

CBS, May 2024